

Recently Identified Small 4Q84 (4QPsalms^b) Fragments from Qumran Cave 4

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version 2

The following four fragments have not been included in the DJD 16 edition of 4Q84 (4QPsalms^b), but have been recently identified.

1. PAM 43.672 frag. 69. IAA Plate 83, frag. 69.

For published image, cf. DJD 33, Pl. XIII (PAM 43.672; cf. www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285451). No transcription was given in DJD 33. New photographic images: www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493470 (full spectrum color image) and www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493471 (infrared image).

Transcription:

[י עת לחנ]׃

[רצו עב]

The fragment fits in 4Q84 col. XX lines 10-11, in the hole in between frags. 16, 17, and 18, while many letters are partially on one and partially on another fragment. Cf. DJD 16, p. 37 and Pl. IV.

These lines can now be transcribed as follows (Ps 102:14b-15a)

כי עת לחננה כי בא מועד 10

כי רצו עב[די]ך את א[בניו] 11

2. PAM 43.688 frag. 108. IAA Plate 81, frag. 105.

For published image, cf. DJD 33, Pl. XXVII (PAM 43.688; cf. www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285463). A transcription was given in DJD 33, p. 210. New photographic images: www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493186 (full spectrum color image) and www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493187 (infrared image).

Transcription:

[וכל קרב]

The fragment fits in 4Q84 col. XXII line 12, where its top edge joins to the bottom edge of 4Q84 frag. 22. Cf. DJD 16, p. 39 and Pl. IV.

This line can now be transcribed as follows (Ps 103:1b)

וכל קרבי את שם קדשו 12

3. PAM 43.661 frag. 50.

For published image, cf. DJD 33, Pl. II (PAM 43.661; cf. www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285440). No transcription was given in DJD 33. No new photographs images are publicly available

Transcription:

]אֹ לַנְּצַחַּ
]לֹ [לֹ [

The fragment fits in 4Q84 col. XXIII lines 11-12, where right and bottom edge join to 4Q84 frag. 21. Cf. DJD 16, p. 41 and Pl. IV.

These lines can now be transcribed as follows (Ps 103:9)

לֹא לַנְּצַחַּ [יָרִיב] 11
וְלֹא לֹ [עוֹלָם יְטוֹר] 12

4. 4Q176 frag. 40. IAA Plate 293, frag. 17.

For published image, cf. DJD 5, Pl. XXIII (based on PAM 43.435; cf. www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284468). Transcription given in DJD 5, p. 66. New photographic images: www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-295149 (full spectrum color image) and www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-295715 (infrared image). This identification was also published as appendix in Tigchelaar (2019:9).

Transcription:

]בְּשֵׁנָא
] אָדָם
]ֹ [

The fragment fits in 4Q84 col. XXXIV lines 13-15, where where its top edge joins to the right bottom edge of frag. 31, and its right edge joints to the left edge of frag. 28. Cf. DJD 16, p. 45 and Pl. VI.

These lines can now be transcribed as follows (Ps 118:7-9):

יְהוָה לִי בְעִזְרִי אֲנִי אֶרְאֶה בְּשֵׁנָא 13
טוֹב לְבַטַח בִּיהוָה מִבַּטַח בְּאָדָם 14
טוֹב לְחַסוֹת בִּיהוָה מִבַּטַח בְּ[גְדִי] בְּ[יָם] 15

References:

- DJD 5 John M. Allegro, *Qumran Cave 4, I*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 5 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1968)
- DJD 16 Eugene Ulrich et al., *Qumran Cave 4, XI: Psalms to Chronicles*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 16 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2000)
- DJD 33 Dana Pike and Andrew Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001)
- IAA Israel Antiquities Authority (used for reference to Plate numbers with scrolls fragments). Fragment numbers are those given by the IAA in The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, deadseascrolls.org.il
- PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum (used for references to PAM photographs). Fragment numbers are those given in the DJD volumes.
- Tigchelaar 2019 Eibert Tigchelaar, "Lamentations 4:21-22 as Another Word of Consolation in 4Q176," *Revue de Qumran* 32/113, 3-9.